

CASE STUDY

POLAND SYNDROME IN A NIGERIAN WOMAN. REPORT OF A CASE.

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INTRODUCTION

Poland's syndrome was described following the work of Sir Alfred Poland in the 19th century as a chest wall deformity showing absence of the sternocostal origin of the pectoralis major, pectoralis minor, serratus anterior and external oblique muscles. However breast hypoplasia/aplasia, nipple asymmetry and hand deformities which were subsequently observed, were not noted. (Fokin 2002) The condition has been ascribed to embryologic accidents occurring in the first trimester leading to development anomaly of the subclavian artery or its branches. (Fokin 2002) An incidence estimated at between 1 in 7000 and 1 in 100,000 has been reported. (Fokin 2002) Workers have defined other characterising conditions to include absence of subcutaneous tissue, brachysyndactyly, unilateral absence of axillary and mammary hair. (Ravitch 1977) Nevertheless, extreme variability has been noted in its presentation. (Urschel 2002)

We report a case of Poland's syndrome seen in a 21 year old lady in Delta, Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Poland's syndrome, breast, hypoplasia.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 21 year old lady presented with an absence of the left breast. She had lived with this condition for as long as she could remember. There was no family history of a similar condition. Examination showed a healthy looking young lady with improvised left breast prosthesis. Breast examination showed an absence of the right breast but a fully developed left breast. The right nipple/areola was hypoplastic and elevated in comparison to the contralateral side. Musculoskeletal examination did not show any bony deformity in the limbs or rib cage. Chest xray showed a well formed rib cage with costal components. However an absent right breast shadow was noted.

DISCUSSION

Although our case occurred in a young female patient, a female /male ratio at 1:2 -1:3 has been described. (Azner 1996) Our case had no family history of the condition, concurring with the largely non-genetic nature of the syndrome. However, a positive family history has been reported in at least 20 cases in world literature. (Velez 2000) This unilateral condition has been reported to be right sided in 60-75% of cases as in our case. (Fokin 2002) However, an isolated bilateral case has been described in the literature.⁶ Our case presented in adult life being concerned about the cosmetic aspect of a right sided hypoplasia in comparison to the contralateral fully developed breast. A spectrum extending from mild hypoplasia to amastia has been reported in more than one-third of female patients with Poland syndrome. (Walker 1969) Although the right side showed characteristic elevated, hypoplastic nipple and areola, supernumerary nipples were not present as has been demonstrated in some cases. (Fokin 2002)

Our case demonstrated a normal rib cage on chest xray, however the breast shadow was unsurprisingly absent. There have been reports of chest deformity being common place in this condition, contributing to cosmetic disfigurement. (Fokin 2002) This has been determined to be due to hypoplasia of the involved ribs and costal cartilages. (Fokin 2002) Aplasia involving up to three ribs with severe chest wall depression has been reported to occur in up to a quarter of the cases. (Walker 1969) Reports of an absence of the pectoralis major, suggests this is a defining feature of this congenital anomaly. (Fokin 2002) Although our case had a hypoplastic right breast, monitoring for early detection of breast cancer is on course for our case. Few reports of invasive ductal carcinoma occurring in the hypoplastic breast suggests that it is susceptible to disease processes of normal breast tissue. (Fukushima 1998) Other oncologic conditions including leukaemias, lymphomas, cervical cancers,

leiomyosarcoma and lung cancers have also been reported in association with Polands syndrome. (Ravitch 1990, Ahn 2000)

An absence of limb deformities in our case suggests a less severe form of polands syndrome; the syndrome being described as a hand and ipsilateral thorax syndrome. Thus the condition has been described to be extremely variable in severity and manifestation. (Urschel 2000)

Clinical

1 photograph showing right breast hypoplasia Chest xray showing intact rib cage with absent right breast shadow.

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